

STRUCTURE OF THE CONNOTATION COMPONENTS IN THE ADJECTIVES

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Abstract: This article underscores the importance of contextualizing the connotation within the linguistic dimension necessitated by the need to generalize the theoretical framework of the concept, to distinguish between broad and narrow meaning of the connotation, to characterize its meaningful content and to define its scope and limits. Based on the abovementioned core issues it is important to consider the adjective as one of the most connotatively colored parts of speech, determining the structure of the connotation components in the adjectives through the lens of language and speech system.

Keywords: connotation, synthesis, definitive analysis, expressive, emotional, evaluative, functional, lexical-semantic category

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Abstract: В данной статье подчеркивается важность контекстуализации коннотации в лингвистическом измерении, обусловленная необходимостью обобщить теоретические рамки понятия, разграничить широкое и узкое значение коннотации, охарактеризовать ее смысловое содержание и определить ее объем и пределы. Исходя из вышеперечисленных основных вопросов, важно рассматривать прилагательное как одну из наиболее коннотативно окрашенных частей речи, определяющую структуру коннотативных компонентов в прилагательных через призму языка и речевого строя.

Keywords: коннотация, синтез, дефинитивный анализ, экспрессивная, эмоциональная, оценочная, функциональная, лексико-семантическая категория.

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Language may influence the perception and recall of things and events through many aspects of its structure. One source of influence is through systems of classification. Any lexical or grammatical marker constitutes a classifier if it has a greater than chance correlation with semantic determinants or with determinants in the social situation of speech.

Various meanings of the term “connotation” pointed out by different scientists are provided, the definition and examples of their lexical and semantic meaning rows is given. Apart from that, the author discusses the phenomenon of secondary metaphoric nomination and its impact on the formation of the imaginative worldview *of the nation using the language*. The research in this sphere is to result in a great contribution to the development of lexicography and the systematical studies of different languages. Incorporation of linguistic units with the meaning of national cultural component is offered in comparing English with Uzbek.

The lexical contrast of "man" vs. "woman" is a classifier for a semantic difference, and the choice is predictable if we control the referent, by asking informants to name people or pictures of men and women. The contrast of "cat" vs. "kitty" is a classifier correlated with social determinants, and the choice is predictable if we control the audience of speech [1].

The aim of the article is to analyze the approaches used to define the term «connotation» through the adjective semantics.

The research methods include analysis, synthesis observation, definitive analysis, linguistic description of linguistic facts, and classification.

The current body of research is analyzed that allowed us to summarize the theoretical elaboration of connotation, to characterize the concept content, and to substantiate its optimal definition. When generalizing the approaches used to differentiate between a broad and a narrow meaning of the connotation, the synthesis of both approaches is underscored. The two types of the connotation – the usual (regular) and occasional (author's) connotation are identified [2]. The structure of the adjective connotation in language and communication is determined. In the language system, the adjective connotation structure is represented by three components including expressive, emotional and evaluative components, while in communication the adjective connotation structure includes four components namely expressive, emotional, evaluative and functional.

The originality of the research lies in an attempt to summarize different approaches used to analyze the connotation, to substantiate the optimal definition of the connotation concept, and to determine the connotation structure of the adjectives in language and communication.

The research prospect can be seen in explaining the ways in which the connotation is expressed in the adjective semantics.

The lexical and semantic system of the language is constantly undergoing changes, since there are it is most sensitive to all changes in society and in the speech consciousness of its native speakers. Connotation as the lexical-semantic category has an ambiguous interpretation due to the contradictory component potential, industry-specific multi-vector representation, and pragmatic supportability. Clarification of the concept of connotation in the linguistic dimension is considered relevant with considering the need to generalize the problems of the current state of its theoretical study, distinguish between a broad and narrow understanding of connotation, characterize its content and define the volume and boundaries. In this regard the projection on the adjective as one of the most connotatively colored parts of speech, defining the structure of components connotations of adjectives in the language and speech system.

Linguistic tradition and the latest scientific developments concepts interpret connotation differently, which is due to different approaches to finding out its specifics and status. The nature of the connotation, its component composition, Semantic potential was studied in the works of Y. D. Apresyan, L. Bloomfield, Sh. Bally, V. I. Hoverdovsky, V. M. Telia, V. I. Shakhovsky and others.

Today, various theories of connotation are presented in the scientific literature, the most famous of which are 3 of which are linguistic (L. Bloomfield, V. G. Gak, V. I. Hoverdovsky, V. M. Telia, B. I. Shakhovsky et al.), psychological (O.M.Leontsv, O. R. Luria, etc.), stylistic (M. P. Brandes, T. G. Vinokur, M. V. Gamzyuk, L. I. Matsko), semiotic (L. T. Yelmslev, R. Bart) and filosofskaya (V. Z. Panfilov, G. V. Kolshansky). Representatives of the linguistic connotation theories explore different language levels: lexical, lexical-grammatical, word- creative, stylistic, communicative, the components of which are components of connotative

The basic unit of language is the word. According to V.V.Vinogradov's definition, "a word as a unit of vocabulary is a unity of a sign, that is, its sound and graphic shell, and its meaning is a specific linguistic reflection of reality". A similar definition is given by D.E. Rosenthal and O.S. Akhmanova "The meaning of a word is the meaning contained in the word, the content associated with the concept as a reflection in the mind of objects and phenomena of the objective world".

The purpose of the article is to make an analytical review of the approaches presented in linguistics to definition of the term "connotation" in the essay on the semantics of an adjective.

Achieving this goal will be facilitated by the implementation of the following tasks:

- 1) generalize problems of the current state of theoretical study of connotation;
- 2) to characterize content of the term "connotation", justify its optimal definition;
- 3) generalize approaches to distinguishing between a broad and narrow understanding of connotation;
- 4) determine the structure of the components of the connotation of adjectives in the system of speech and speech.

Writers often use connotation to create emotional associations that can be either positive, negative, or neutral.

1. Positive connotation. Words that conjure a favorable emotional response. For example, *describing someone ambitious as a "go-getter" or someone who is lively and curious as "youthful."*

2. Negative connotation. When a negative connotation is made, it presents the person or thing in an unfavorable light. Using the examples above, the

same ambitious person might be described as an "overachiever," while the curious person might be referred to as "childish."

3. Neutral connotation. This is when a word says what it means with a neutral point of view, and no attached positive or negative connotation. The statement, "He is ambitious" suggests a person works hard and strives to achieve, without judgment on whether the ambition is a good or a bad thing.

In the course of the study, both general scientific methods are involved, so are purely linguistic methods: analysis and synthesis - to substantiate the theoretical foundations observation-to provide the research process with empirical information; a method of definitive analysis that determines the content of scientific definitions the concept of connotation; linguistic description of language facts - for inventory and systematization different approaches to distinguishing between a broad and narrow understanding of connotation; comparative -to compare different definitions of the concept of "connotation".

In modern linguistics there is no unanimity on the definition of connotation in the semantic structure of a language unit. Term "connotation" was first used in research on logic in the XIX century. this phenomenon was studied J. S. Mill [3], but the term received its linguistic status in the works of L. Bloomfield.

The interpretation of the connotation proposed by the linguist pointed to a specific level of language, due to cultural, social, regional and other factors, i.e. the researcher first began to associate connotation with the emotionality of speech [4].

The founder of the study of connotation as a concept of phonetic Stylistics rightly considered S. Bally, whose works are devoted to topical problems of Psychologically motivated relationships between sounds and emotional layers [5]. Later R. Bart noted that the future is based on connotative semiotics, since in society on the basis of systems of secondary meanings are constantly emerging from the primary system of natural language [6].

Already in the twentieth century. many linguists, including L. T. Yelmslev [7], V. I. Hoverdovsky [8], I. A. Sternin [9] et al., raised the problems of generating connotation as constructive an element of transcoding the semantic plane of the language with an additional value, and Y. D. Apresyan [10], V. I. Shakhovsky [11], V. O. Buldakov [12] and others specified necessity of the emotive-evaluative function of connotative elements of language units capable of represent the communicative-situational stratification of speech.

It is concluded that the connotation is an additional semantic, emotional, pragmatic or stylistic shade of meaning that is of usual or occasional type, adds to word semantics and expresses an emotionally-evaluative attitude toward your subject. The connotation actively participates in the expressive-emotional-

evaluative nomination; it also creates a new secondary meaning to the word in communication which is subsequently assimilated by language.

REFERENCES:

1. Haydarov, Anvar Askarovich and Navruzova, Nigina Hamidovna (2021) "STYLISTIC FEATURES OF INTONATION," Scientific reports of Bukhara State University: Vol. 5 : Iss. 1 , Article 2, 18-29. DOI: 10.52297/2181-1466/2021/5/1/2 <https://uzjournals.edu.uz/buxdu/vol5/iss1/2>
2. Mirzo Makhmudovich Tursunov. (2022). ANALYSIS OF SOME ENGLISH IDIOMS CONTAINING POPULAR PROPER NAMES. European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development, 5, 62-67. <http://ejird.journalspark.org/index.php/ejird/article/view/98>
3. Khaydarov, Anvar Askarovich (2020) "EXPRESSION OF CONNOTATIVE MEANING IN ONOMATOPOEIA," Scientific reports of Bukhara State University: Vol. 4 : Iss. 5 , Article 5, 76-80. DOI: 10.52297/2181-1466/2020/4/5/5 <https://uzjournals.edu.uz/buxdu/vol4/iss5/5>
4. Рахматова, М. М. (2018). ВЫРАЖЕНИЕ КОНЦЕПТА " НЕКРАСИВОСТЬ (ХУНУКЛИК)" В ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННЫХ ТЕКСТАХ В УЗБЕКСКОЙ ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРЕ И ЕГО ЛЕКСИКО-СЕМАНТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ. Теория и практика современной науки, (3), 295-299. <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=34883609>
5. Askarovich, H. A. (2021). EXPRESSION OF CONNOTATIVE MEANING IN GRAPHIC MEANS. International Engineering Journal For Research & Development, 6 (TITFL), 91-94. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/3Q7SB>
6. Nazarova Navbahor Ahrorovna. (2022). SEMANTIC PROPERTIES OF ANTHROPONYMS. Indonesian Journal of Innovation Studies, 18. <https://doi.org/10.21070/ijins.v18i.626>
<https://ijins.umsida.ac.id/index.php/ijins/article/view/626>
7. Rasulov, Z. (2022). ОБ ОБЪЕКТЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ КОГНИТИВНОЙ СЕМАНТИКИ. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 8(8).
извлечено от http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/4346
8. Navruzova, N. (2022). ПОДХОДЫ К ЛЕКСИЧЕСКИМ КОННОТАЦИЯМ. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 8(8). http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/4356
9. Khamidovna, N. N. (2022). THE DENOTATION AND CONNOTATION OF A WORD. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(4), 382-388. <https://wos.academiascience.org/index.php/wos/article/view/1242>

10. Наврузова, Н. Х. (2022). KONNOTATIV MA'NONING BADIY ASARLARDA IFODALANISHI: Navruzova Nigina Xamidovna, Buxoro davlat universiteti Ingliz tilshunosligi kafedrası o'qituvchisi. Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал, (7). <https://www.interscience.uz/index.php/home/article/view/1490>

10. Kilichev, B. E. A Way of Making Words on Proper Nouns. International Journal on Integrated Education, 3(2), 96-98. <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/333098-a-way-of-making-words-on-proper-nouns-08e83e0e.pdf>

11. Tursunov, M. (2022). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ГИПОРБОЛЕ В РАЗНЫХ ЛИТЕРАТУРНЫХ ЖАНРАХ. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 22(22). ИЗВЛЕЧЕНО ОТ http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/7959

12. Xamidovna, N. N. (2021). Approaches to lexical connotations. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(10), 1721-1726. <https://www.indianjournals.com/ijor.aspx?target=ijor:aca&volume=11&issue=10&article=258>

13. Akramov, I. (2022). AFORIZIMLARNING LINGVISTIK JANR SIFATIDA RIVOJLANISHI. ILMIY NASHRLAR MARKAZI (buxdu.Uz), 8(8). Retrieved from http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/5690

14. Yuldasheva Feruza Erkinovna. (2022). The Principle of Politeness in the English and Uzbek Languages. Eurasian Research Bulletin, 6, 65-70. Retrieved from <https://www.geniusjournals.org/index.php/erb/article/view/799>

15. O'rinbekovna, U. M. (2022). INGLIZ TILIDA FRAZEOLGIK BIRLIKLARNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI. Journal of new century innovations, 15(1), 73-80.

16. Kodirova Kholida Khayriddin kizi. (2022). The Analysis of Illocutionary Acts in Adventures of Tom Sawyer by Mark Twain. Miasto Przyszłości, 28, 324-328. <http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/648>

17. Nargiza Bobojonova Jumaniyozovna. (2022). The Term Concept in Modern Linguistics. Miasto Przyszłości, 28, 297-302. <http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/643>

18. Djumayeva, N. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MAGICAL JEWELLERY AND ORNAMENTS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK FAIRY TALES. JournalNX- A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal ISSN No: 2581 - 4230.VOLUME 7, ISSUE 6, June. -2021,138-142. <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/347771-comparative-analysis-of-magical-jeweller-8838f05c.pdf>